

Gradation of Cosmic Rays

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Abstract:

Humans follow the diurnal rhythm of the sun to form an internal rhythm of 24-hour cycles. On the other hand, when such restrictions are removed, an internal rhythm of 25-hour cycles reminiscent of the lunar cycle emerges. In addition, women's menstrual cycles are also seen to be in sync with the monthly rhythms. In order to elucidate the truth behind these events, I created a new theoretical system (gradation theory) by combining the two facts of the orbital motion

of the moon and the cosmic ray arrival. By applying it, I found that the human body rhythm is formed in dependence on external factors. In addition, a logical answer was derived from it about the nature of sleep. In the future, sleep will take an increasingly prominent place in human endeavors.

Keywords: *Diurnal Rhythm, Lunar Rhythm, Biological Clock, Cosmic Rays, Cave Experiments, Gradation Theory.*

Introduction

The earth orbits the sun while also rotating on its own axis. This, combined with the tilt of the earth's axis, produces the four seasons and a circadian rhythm with a 24-hour cycle. Living creatures on the earth form various biological rhythms to adapt to such an environment. Some organisms are diurnal, active during the day, while others are nocturnal, active at night. Both have completed their own internal clocks (Minoru, 2020), using as a guide the gradations of sunlight intensity that transform in various ways depending on the time of day. We humans also have such internal rhythms. In other words, every day we achieve a regular life by repeating our activities during the day and sleeping at night.

However, interesting data were presented in this connection. That is the result of an experiment in which the internal rhythms of the human body were measured in a cave. Subjects are placed in a closed room, isolated from the outside world, and allowed to live. The researcher then

observes how they form their internal rhythms. As a result, their biological rhythm was found to be a 25-hour cycle (Kuniaki, 2012). Dividing one month (approximately 744 hours) by 29.5 days, which is the lunar rhythm, yields approximately 25, which suggests that this is in sync with the lunar rhythm. In addition, since women's menstrual rhythm is a 28-38 day cycle (Masako et al., 2008), it would seem that there is also some relationship with the monthly cycle rhythm.

This raises the question of whether there is some mechanism that relates biological rhythms to lunar rhythms.

Methodology

Originally, most marine organisms were known to live in an approximately 25-hour rhythm (Gabriele, & Kristin, 2020). It is thought that this is because sunlight is blocked by seawater and does not reach their bodies, so instead they chose the information with some periodicity brought by the moon as a guide. If so, the 25-

hour cycle of the subjects in the cave experiment could be based on the same reason. In short, instead of sunlight, which cannot penetrate shields such as seawater or bedrock, there is some information that can clear them and reach the organism's bodies, which controls such rhythm formation.

However, it is unlikely that such information is emanating from the moon. Therefore, a bold shift in thinking is needed. In other words, we should think of the moon not as transmitter of such information, but as the interceptor of information coming from another, true source. The moon is not the transmitter, but the interferer.

What in the world?

Of cosmic rays, that is.

Cosmic rays are high-energy radiation that comes to Earth from all parts of the universe (Kouzou, 2018). They are protons, electrons, neutrinos, etc. The particles and heavy particles scattered in all directions as stars end their lives and explode into supernovas are cosmic rays. Its radiation sources are everywhere in the universe, and constant supernova explosions mean that it is constantly pouring down on Earth. Some of them are highly permeable, and they easily penetrate the human brain and body. We are unknowingly exposed to cosmic rays every hour of every day.

It is thought that the Moon not only functions to shield such cosmic rays as an interceptor before they reach the Earth, but also actively absorbs them with its own gravity. If so, as the moon as a disturbance orbits the earth in a period of about 29.5 days, the 25-hour rhythm should produce differences in the shading of the cosmic ray flux. From there, a new concept of cosmic ray gradation is derived. In other words, when there is a moon in the sky, the amount of cosmic ray flux is reduced because it is blocked by the moon. On the other hand, when there is no moon in the sky, there is nothing to block the cosmic rays, so the cosmic ray flux increases. If the distinction between more and less is arranged in layers of detail, it appears as a gradation. It is thought that such gradual

changes in the shading of cosmic rays appear on the earth at a 25-hour rhythm. In sync with this, the subjects trapped in the caves and marine organisms are assumed to be resetting their biological clocks to a 25-hour rhythm. I named such a new hypothesis the "Gradation Theory".

In this regard, the object of the guideline differs between the case of female menstrual rhythms and the case of cave subjects and marine organisms. A women's menstrual rhythm is formed using the orbital motion of the moon as a guide. Hence, its cycle would be a 28-38 day rhythm. On the other hand, the lunar rhythm of cave subjects and marine organisms must be considered in combination with the orbital motion of the Moon and the Earth's rotation. Cave subjects and marine organisms cannot know information about sunlight. Hence, they try to synchronize with the lunar rhythm, but when the earth carrying them makes one rotation in 24 hours, the moon, which was in the same position in the sky, is not there. This is because the moon is moving further ahead in its orbital motion. For the moon to visible at the same position in the sky as the previous day, the earth must spend an additional hour to rotate to that position. In other words, for the moon to be a regular guide for them, the earth would have to keep moving for 25 hours straight. In a world cut off from sunlight, the earth's rotation period is, in effect, a 25-hour cycle. Living creatures use this rhythm as a guide to synchronize their own internal clocks with it.

As described above, by applying the gradation theory, we can explain why women's menstrual cycles and the internal rhythms of marine organisms and cave subjects are formed.

If so, the following would be true. There are those who advocate a plan to migrate to Mars. They argue that we should move to Mars, a planet much like Earth, in case Earth experiences a population explosion and its resources are depleted. However, Mars has two satellites, Phobos and Deimos (Hiromichi, 2018). Let us apply gradation theory to that. The people living there would then experience a different cosmic ray rhythm than on Earth. Since the Earth has only the Moon as a satellite, if they

start living on Mars, they will have to form a biological clock that is more complicated than before. However, it will take many years for this to happen, and the human mind and body will not be able to withstand the sudden and dramatic changes in the environment, which will lead to serious disorders, such as cancer and depression. Also, women's menstrual cycles would be disrupted, so reproductive activities would not run smoothly, and the human race would perish. Thus, from the perspective of the biological clock, migration to Mars is indeed a foolish measure. For earthlings, living on earth is the best way to live.

In addition, orbiting satellites, space stations, and space debris in space above the earth may affect cosmic ray gradation by shielding cosmic rays coming from space. This could cause a malfunction in the internal rhythms of the creatures living on the earth. It is best to refrain from releasing artifacts into Earth's orbit.

On the other hand, what about life on the moon? Since the Moon has no satellites, cosmic rays flying to the lunar surface are uniform and do not form gradients. Hence, it is the solar rhythm that humans should be attuned to. However, the Moon's rotation period coincides with its orbital period (Kenji, Hideharu, & Shinichi, 2003), which means that one day on the Moon is equivalent to 29.5 days on Earth. This means that the diurnal rhythm there is a 29.5-day cycle. Whether this is useful as a guide to the biological clock is highly questionable. If we follow this, human life can be viewed as about 19 days of continuous sleepless activity, followed by 10 days of continuous sleep. Therefore, repeating it over and over again would only cause exhaustion.

After all, it is happiest for earthlings to live on earth.

Discussion

As mentioned earlier, marine organisms have only the lunar rhythm (cosmic ray gradation) as an indicator to rely on, and they use it as the basis for their internal clocks. Humans, on the other hand, are in a position to take advantage of both

lunar and diurnal rhythms. Originally, it should be sufficient for humans living on land to set their body clocks to a 24-hour rhythm according to the solar rhythm. However, as can be seen from the results of the cave experiment, the human body is structured in such a way that it can also utilize lunar rhythms. The natural world and human body have a marvelous sense of balance and will always degenerate useless or disused organs. The seemingly useless human function of responding to lunar rhythms would have disappeared long ago if it were truly unnecessary, yet it persists.

The question, then, is what are the reasons for this, in relation to the essential theory of sleep.

The mechanism by which humans take sunlight into their bodies to form a biological clock with a 24-hour cycle is accomplished by several organs. They are the retina of both eyes, the optic nerve, the suprachiasmatic nucleus, and the pineal gland (Kuniaki, 2012). Light information is caught by the retina, converted into electrical signals, and sent through the optic nerve to organs such as the suprachiasmatic nucleus and pineal gland. As a result, various hormones are secreted and interact with various parts of the brain. This process is repeated in a 24-hour cycle (Minoru, 2020). This is the body clock system that is in sync with the diurnal rhythm.

However, when humans fall asleep at night, they close their eyes, shutting out all light information. Sunlight is high-energy and essential to human vitality, but it is cut off during sleep. This would require some kind of new energy to be introduced into the body to replace it. That is cosmic ray energy.

It is thought that the human body takes in cosmic ray energy to compensate for the loss of solar energy when falling sleep.

However, during sleep, the retina, optic nerve, suprachiasmatic nucleus, and other organs that were working when the diurnal rhythm was formed by sunlight are not available because the eyelids are closed.

Therefore, it is necessary to clarify how the human body take in cosmic rays as a source of vitality. I have the following hypothesis about it.

Cosmic rays have high penetrating power. Hence, penetrating the skull, it reaches directly to various areas in the brain. Various types of interactions occur there, bringing great benefits to the human body. In other words, it can be thought of as follows. Unlike sunlight, which is delivered indirectly to the brain through the retina and optic nerve, cosmic rays are delivered directly to the brain, producing electrical pulses and various hormone secretions, just as neutrinos interact in water to produce Cherenkov light.

The human body is transformed into a new self through such benefits through sleep (Junichi, 2023). Of course, it is expected that the degree of neuronal activation in the brain will differ during non-REM sleep and REM sleep (Newton Press, 2021). But in any case, we can see from this that sleep is not a worthless and futile activity that produces nothing, but a valuable and active act that allows the human body to survive in autonomous harmony.

As we have seen above, sleep is important for the human body and should be actively practiced. The source of its vitality is thought to be the high energy of cosmic rays. It is both beneficial and reasonable for them to penetrate the skull and act directly on the brain as a biological individual.

That being so, the human body will not give up its ability to respond to cosmic rays (the ability to respond to lunar rhythms). This is why the body clocks of cave subjects are on a 25-hour cycle.

Results

Since the cave experiment changed the human body rhythm to a 25-hour cycle, I focused on the relationship between that and the lunar rhythm and developed a hypothesis to explain it. In view of the penetrating power of cosmic rays, it acts directly on the brain, but not all cosmic rays can penetrate the moon itself and fly to the earth. Therefore, coupled with the orbital motion of the moon, a gradation of “transmitted” and “non-transmitted” cosmic rays is formed. After making such assumptions, I was able to

successfully explain how the female menstrual cycle and the internal rhythms of cave subjects and marine organisms are formed by synchronizing with them.

Conclusion

Humans have a rhythm of life in which they are active during the day and sleep at night. They are an activity to attune with the surrounding nature and universe. The table summarizes the following (Table 1).

Table 1. Synchronization Medium of the Human Body to Nature

Day (activity)	Sunlight
Night (sleep)	Cosmic rays

Thus, the synchronization means (synchronization medium) is only different between activity and sleep, but the fundamentals are the same. Both are important activities that are indispensable for maintaining harmony in the human body.

If so, it goes without saying that putting sleep in an inferior position to daytime activities and cutting back on it is a major enemy in keeping you healthy, young, and beautiful. The two must be treated in the same manner in terms of value, and should not be treated as superior or inferior.

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